
Gender diversity in European DeepTech Accelerator Programmes

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Abstract: Over the years, women have become a significant part of the workforce, but they had to overcome a lot of barriers and challenges to succeed in their career development. The barriers that they are faced with have been widely acknowledged, urging researchers and practitioners to focus on identifying ways to minimize gender inequality. Up until now, the employment context has received most attention. Yet, there is evidence that this is also the case for the entrepreneurship domain. Even though, in the last few years women are more actively pursuing entrepreneurship, many challenges are still at place. Specifically, gender bias, limited government support and limited funding make entrepreneurship harder for women than for men. Thus, several actors of the European entrepreneurship ecosystem (such as incubators and business accelerators) are trying to eliminate this gap, by promoting specific funding programs, events, and policies. However, whether these strategies do effectively support women in entrepreneurship remains unclear. The objective of our study is to underscore the potential of European DeepTech Accelerators to foster a gender-neutral environment. The study took place among 49 European business accelerators, from 20 different European countries as a part of the EU funded

project entitle ‘Acceleration’¹. Measuring gender inequality both in terms of the percentage of women (co)-founders in their portfolio and percentage of invested start-ups with a woman as a (co)-founder, revealed that most of the accelerators still exhibit high or moderate gender inequality. Only few of them run exclusive programs and provide support adapted to women entrepreneurs. Additionally, accelerators with moderate to high success rates for startups led or co-led by women seem to use similar communication strategies to those used by accelerators with lower success rates. Apparently, accelerators which run activities tailored to women entrepreneurs, showcase significant differences in their provisions, requests, team composition and communication strategy. The study reveals that gender inequality is still apparent in many European DeepTech accelerators. However, those with tailored programs for women entrepreneurs show significant differences in their practices. This suggests that customized activities and targeted communication strategies are crucial for effectively supporting women in entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Europe; DeepTech; Accelerators; gender inclusivity

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is a major driver of economic growth and development (Lee et al., 2004); however, launching a new venture often proves more challenging for women, who are generally less likely than men to pursue entrepreneurship, secure investor funding, and achieve long-term success (Guzman and Kacperczyk, 2019; Ruef et al., 2003; Coleman and Robb, 2009; GEM, 2023). This disparity is evident globally. According to a recent study, from 2018 to 2022 only about 6% of working women in the EU and 9% in OECD countries were involved in starting or managing a new business, compared to 8% of men in the EU and 11% of men in OECD nations (OECD, 2023).

The challenge of accessing capital further exacerbates these inequalities, especially in equity funding, where a significant and persistent gap remains in venture capital rates between women and men-led businesses, creating additional barriers to women’s entrepreneurial success (Brush et al., 2018).

The factors responsible for this gender gap are complex, culturally embedded and intertwined, including differences in motivations, resources and skills owned, access to external resources, social attitudes towards work and entrepreneurship, local labour market conditions, opportunities in employment, as well as the uneven impact of policies and regulations and the societal structure (Bullough et al., 2019; Marlow and McAdam, 2012; Martínez-Rodríguez et al., 2021).

To near the gap in performance in entrepreneurship is a top priority for governments because this would allow economic independence for women and also contribute to development, growth and innovation (OECD, 2023). If women participated in early-stage entrepreneurship at rates comparable to men, this could yield an additional 5.5 million women entrepreneurs in the EU and 24.8 million in OECD countries. Recent estimates from

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Canada and the United Kingdom further suggest that achieving gender parity in business creation and growth could enhance GDP by approximately 6% to 12%. (OECD, 2023).

With that scope, governments together with non-governmental organisations and the private sector, have been implementing policies and delivering programmes to support women entrepreneurship, including ambassador, promotional campaigns, training, meetings with potential role models, peer-learning programmes, coaching and mentoring, financial supports and microcredit, with alternate results and often minor impact (Bullough et al., 2019). Additionally, to overcome financial biases in favour of male entrepreneurs, female investors and advisors and funds led by women could also be helpful (Halabisky, 2018). Among them, accelerators and incubators play a pivotal role acting as intermediaries in the given entrepreneurial ecosystem, positively influencing the start-up they support (Hallen et al., 2014).

The goal of our study is to highlight the potential of European DeepTech Accelerators to create a gender-neutral environment by assessing gender inequality in terms of the proportion of invested start-ups with a female co-founder and the percentage of women (co)-founders in their portfolio.

Gender disparities in DeepTech entrepreneurship

The role of accelerators

Accelerators and incubators structures and scopes often overlap. Incubators are shared workspaces that provide startups with structured support, often referred to as business incubation, to help them grow successfully. This support system connects startups with critical resources, aiming to boost their chances of success, while minimizing the costs associated with potential failures (Hackett and Dilts, 2004).

Incubators offer to new businesses access to (1) physical resources, (2) administrative services, (3) funding opportunities, (4) guidance on business processes, and (5) valuable networking connections. These elements help startups overcome early challenges and increase their survival rates (Schwartz, 2013). Incubators' role is fundamental for fostering entrepreneurial success on a global scale (Dutt et al., 2016; Hansen et al., 2000). These organizations serve as institutional intermediaries, effectively bridging the gap between incubated entrepreneurs — often referred to as “incubatees”— and various stakeholders within the broader business ecosystem (Dutt et al., 2016). This interconnected network is essential for the development and growth of new ventures.

Within the incubator environment, a dynamic range of formal and informal interactions occurs among incubatees, incubator managers, external resource providers, and industry experts. These interactions facilitate the exchange of critical information and insights, which are vital for the entrepreneurial process (Dutt et al., 2016). By creating spaces for dialogue and collaboration, incubators encourage knowledge sharing and help entrepreneurs navigate the complexities of starting and scaling a business. Furthermore, incubators position their incubatees within networks that are rich in information and resources, effectively alerting them to new market opportunities and trends.

Acting as positive endorsements of the business potential inherent in these ventures, incubators enhance the credibility of incubatees in the eyes of potential investors, resource providers, and information holders. This credibility is instrumental in assisting incubatees to mobilize essential resources, such as funding, mentorship, and strategic partnerships (Hansen et al., 2000). Additionally, the mentorship and discussions that take place within incubators serve a dual purpose: they not only impart valuable knowledge and industry insights but also help incubatees develop critical skills. This skill development includes the ability to creatively combine and recombine resources, information, and innovative ideas, fostering an environment conducive to enhanced innovation (Haugh, 2020).

Emphasizing collaboration and resourcefulness, incubators not only support individual ventures but also contribute to the overall health of the entrepreneurial ecosystem. They empower startups to become more resilient and adaptable, which is particularly important in today's rapidly changing business landscape. Ultimately, incubators are instrumental in shaping the future of entrepreneurship, by nurturing the next generation of innovative leaders. In recent years, accelerators have emerged as an advanced form of incubators, with around 8,000 accelerators globally and related investments surpassing \$50 billion in 2018 (Gliedt et al., 2018).

An accelerator is defined as "a fixed-term, cohort-based program, including mentorship and educational components, that culminates in a public pitch event or demo day" (Cohen and Hochberg, 2014, p. 4). Accelerator programs have some defining characteristics that set them apart from incubators and angel investors. They typically involve an open, highly competitive application process, and are of limited duration — usually lasting between three and six months — to promote rapid progress. Within this period, startups undergo structured training programs covering diverse topics, such as finance, marketing, logistics, legal matters, and human resources through lectures, seminars, and workshops. Additionally, participants benefit from mentorship support provided by the program's management team and mentors, who offer business advice, valuable networking opportunities, and introductions to potential investors. Accelerator programs often provide pre-seed investments, typically ranging from \$10,000 to \$50,000, in exchange for equity and access to a wider pool of external investors. Startups are also given a shared office space, fostering peer-to-peer learning and collaboration. Finally, these programs admit startups in cohort batches or 'classes,' focusing on small teams rather than individual entrepreneurs, which encourages collective growth and support among participants (Bagnoli et al., 2020; Cohen et al., 2019; Goldstein et al., 2015; Hochberg, 2016; Miller and Bound, 2011).

Summing up, accelerators "link the context in which they operate with the interventions they deliver and the outcomes they realize" (Crişan et al., 2021, p. 85). Programmes and economic support initiatives may indeed promote and facilitate entrepreneurship broadly; however, it is uncertain whether these efforts reflect a masculine-oriented context or not. In other words, while accelerators aim to encourage and support entrepreneurs, their impact on women entrepreneurs remains ambiguous.

Women entrepreneurs within accelerators and incubators

Dixit and Sinha (2024) underscored the role of incubator and accelerator affiliation in helping women business owners overcome the documented gender-specific challenges in entrepreneurial activities. They posit that women entrepreneurs, especially those from

emerging economies, would benefit significantly from incubators as it would liberate them from patriarchal shackles that might otherwise limit their aspirations and potential to perform entrepreneurial functions. This contribution is bolstered by the fact that those initiatives provide a level playing field for women entrepreneurs. In particular, Dixit and Sinha (2024) found that incubated women outperformed non-incubated women entrepreneurs in conducting entrepreneurial functions such as opportunity recognition, resource mobilization, and innovation with no difference between incubated men and women entrepreneurs in conducting them. By addressing the mobility constraints imposed by patriarchal norms, accelerators empower women to visit places and travel, explore information and resource combinations, meet experts, overcome uncertainty, assess feasibility, and take calculated risks, which are critical steps in fostering innovation (Dixit and Sinha, 2024). Above all, incubators and accelerators helped women entrepreneurs reverse the damage caused by societal norms and the constraints of their gender roles. As highlighted by Dixit and Sinha (2024), accelerators beyond entrepreneurial support can alleviate patriarchal constraints on women in emerging economies. Accelerators signal the legitimacy of women-owned businesses and provide them with alternative platforms on which to elevate their social status. This support lifts some of the gender restrictions and contributes significantly to reversing societal hindrances and unlocking women's creative potential. Thus, accelerators can be seen not only as intermediaries to boost entrepreneurship but also as tools for empowering women outside their familial environment, fostering a level playing field for entrepreneurship. Hence, the findings imply that a tailored approach on the part of incubator managers and administrators, rather than a one-size-fits-all strategy, is necessary to support women entrepreneurs.

Recognizing the vital role that incubators and accelerators play as an alternative institutional platform for women entrepreneurs, policymakers should prioritize initiatives to identify and address the barriers hindering women's participation in such incubators. The proposed measures include targeted awareness campaigns to inform women entrepreneurs, especially those in localized contexts who might be unaware of institutional support (Dixit and Sinha, 2024).

One should also consider that entrepreneurship involves a number of stages, from founding a new venture, to seeking capital, to exit. Such understanding is critical for addressing gender inequality in entrepreneurship and increasing female representation among entrepreneurs. If differences between female and male entrepreneurs arise at different stages and accumulate over time, policies should involve numerous interventions, which target multiple actors at multiple stages of the process that is entrepreneurship (Guzman and Kacperczyk, 2019).

Broadening the scope to other scholars, according to Le Loarne Lemaire et al. (2023), incubators and accelerators function as knowledge hubs that facilitate the transfer of information not only from trainers and coaches to women nascent entrepreneurs but also among women entrepreneurs themselves. This interconnectedness fosters collaboration and empowerment within the community of women entrepreneurs.

Conversely, other scholars argue that incubators and accelerators often end up reflecting the systemic disadvantages faced by women entrepreneurs in society as a whole, failing to effectively address and close the gender gap (Brush et al., 2019; Dahlstrand and Politis, 2013). This critique suggests that while incubators and accelerators may provide certain resources, they may not sufficiently challenge or transform the underlying barriers that hinder women's entrepreneurial success. Remaining on this point, also Callerstig et al. (2024) recognize that incubators and accelerators aren't neutral, but present bias as all

human endeavours. The authors add to the complexity of the arguments by reporting that Scandinavian countries, due to their culture and history, do not promote specific programmes dedicated to women because they already believe to treat them completely equal to men, whereas in other countries these tailored programmes would be considered useful.

As highlighted by Callerstig et al. (2024), different countries and their local experience present different approaches. Incubator managers in Norway and Sweden recognise that there is a prevailing gender gap, and they argue that the proportion of women tenants needs to increase. However, in line with the national policies, the Scandinavian incubators put no, or very little emphasis on women-only initiatives and focus on gender mainstreaming and inclusion in a broader sense in order to avoid discrimination or special treatment.

In Ireland and Israel, on the other hand, there are several initiatives specifically targeting women entrepreneurs in the hope of inspiring more and more young women to start their own business.

The authors found that incubators and accelerators, in general, implement policies in line with the stated policies of their respective countries. Consequently, in Norway and Sweden, where the national policies emphasise gender mainstreaming, the incubators and accelerators do not rely on women-only programs. However, this does not mean that the incubators and accelerators fail to recognise the gender gap as a problem. This issue is clarified by Callerstig et. al (2024, p.1693) “We advocate for a shift away from solely focusing on women’s access to resources towards fundamentally changing the structures that perpetuate gender disparities. To initiate this transformation, it is essential to unmask claims of neutrality in policy formulation. This process encourages policymakers to explicitly recognise and address the implicit biases deeply ingrained in current policy frameworks”.

The present research aims to investigate this issue and make a contribution to the existing body of knowledge. By addressing this topic, the study seeks not only to fill current gaps in understanding but also to provide valuable insights and policy implications that can be applied in this field.

Methodology

Data collection was established through an online survey questionnaire, which was administered in the last quarter of 2021 in countries of EU-27. Researchers aimed to contact at least two accelerators from each European Union country with a deep tech perspective. A total of 59 responses were collected. Overall, 49 fully and correctly completed responses were collected (83.5%), coming from 20 European countries (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Respondent Accelerators per country

Concerning the type of accelerators, in line with the European Innovation Scoreboard (European Commission, 2022), most are Emerging Innovators (34.69%) or Moderate Innovators (34.69%), followed by Strong Innovators (22.45%), and Innovation Leaders (8.16%). The average percentage of women (co-)founders that participated in accelerator’s programmes or cohorts laid between 26% to 50%, but the average rate of invested startups with women (co-)founder ranged between 1% and 25%.

Questionnaire Items & Variables

The question items aim to capture whether the accelerators differ in their essential means and tactics to nourish an entrepreneurial environment that is inclusive of all genders, to pinpoint barriers hindering this initiative and to ascertain whether gender inclusivity leads to more successful accelerators (Table 1). Specifically, two variables are employed to gauge the extent of gender inclusivity within Accelerators – percentage of women (co-)founders participated on programmes or cohorts and the percentage of invested startups with a woman as a (co-) founder. Building on this, it is essential to understand whether there are particular factors that lead to success for accelerators based on their level of gender inclusivity. Apart from the marketing strategies that is well know that they can help firms to grow, the human capital is crucial for their performance (Crook et al., 2011). Where human capital is the embodied knowledge in people (Coff, 2002) – which is manifested in their skills and capabilities – and its accumulation is one of the major challenges that firms should overcome to secure a competitive advantage (Campbell et al., 2012; Hatch and Dyer, 2004).

Table 1 Variables

Question	Author(-s)	Field	Scale	Coding
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Select the answer that fits best the gender inclusivity of the Accelerator's all programs/cohorts in 2022: % of women (co-) founders in the portfolio	Neumeyer, (2020)			GINCO
Select the answer that fits best the gender inclusivity of the Accelerator's all programs/cohorts in 2022: % of invested startups with a woman as a (co-) founder	Harrison and Masson (2007); Johnson et al., (2018); Kanze et al., (2018)	Gender Inclusivity	1 = "0%" 2 = "1%-25%" 3 = "26%-50%" 4 = "51%-75%" 5 = "76%-100%"	GINV
The performance of the startups included in the Accelerator (up to now): % of portfolio startups that got funded	Crişan et al., (2021); Lall et al., (2013); Radojevich-Kelley and Hoffman (2012)	Success		SGF
Which aspects correspond to the Accelerator's status - High interaction with relevant public stakeholders (government, regional authorities)	Clarke and MacDonald (2019); Saxton (1997)	Brand Equity		HIRPS
Which mentorship-related aspects did the Accelerator provide to the program participants - startups (in 2022)? - Experienced and/or renowned mentors			1 = "Yes" 0 = "No"	EM
Level of experience & skills for the teams working with startups, in Accelerator (in 2022): Leadership/management team	Crook et al., (2011); Grant, (1996)	Human Capital	1 = "Inexperienced/unqualified" 2 = "Limited experience & skills" 3 = "Some prior experience & with skills" 4 = "Significant experience & skills" 5 = "Highly experienced & qualified"	LELM

As whole, the Accelerator provides to the program participants – startups substantial access to Talent Pool (STEM-focused talent pool for any deeptech startup)]			1 = “Strongly disagree” 2 = “Disagree” 3 = “Neither, nor” 4 = “Agree” 5 = “Strongly agree”	ATP
Number of full-time employers in the Accelerator	Gooding et al. (1985)		Integer	FTE
As whole, the Accelerator provides to the program participants – startups easy access to clients or pilot partners (Ease of Market Access)	Uhm <i>et al.</i> , (2018)	Provisions	1 = “Strongly disagree” 2 = “Disagree” 3 = “Neither, nor” 4 = “Agree” 5 = “Strongly agree”	EMA
The biggest challenges (problematic) for the Accelerator: Human Resource (employees)	Campbell et al., (2012); Luthans and Youssef, (2004)	Challenges	1 = “Very easy” 2 = “easy” 3 = “Neutral” 4 = “Difficult” 5 = “Very difficult”	CHR CCMP
Accelerator provide to the program participants – startups, guaranteed financial grants or investments through a related funding arm	Cohen et al., (2019); Pandey et al., (2017)		1 = “No” 2 = “Yes, to some participants” 3 = “Yes, to all participants”	GFFA
The Accelerator provides to the program participants – startups substantial financing or support access to finance (Financing)		Finance	1 = “Strongly disagree” 2 = “Disagree” 3 = “Neither, nor” 4 = “Agree” 5 = “Strongly agree”	SFIA
Accelerator asked for fees and/or equity stake (shares) from the program participants - startups	Clarysse <i>et al.</i> , (2016); Cohen <i>et al.</i> , (2019)		1 = “No” 2 = “Yes, to some participants” 3 = “Yes, to all participants”	FES
Degree of well known the Accelerator is among B2B, at national level (notoriety)	Bagnoli <i>et al.</i> , (2020)	Marketing	1 = “very low notoriety” 2 = “low” 3 = “average” 4 = “high”	WKN

5 = “very high notoriety”

Paid communication activity using mass-media (e.g. to be broadcasted or displayed offline and online/ newspapers/ TV/ radio/ video sharing platform / podcasts, etc.)				CAP
Sponsored communication activity using own channels of social media and/or browser ads for website	Deighton and Kornfeld, (2009); Lance and Guy (2006); Vieira et al. (2019)	1= “0 actions” 2= “1-2 actions” 3= “3-4 actions” 4= “≥ 5actions”		CAS
Unpaid communication activity using mass-media (e.g. presence with live interviews or press release on offline and online/ newspapers/ TV/ radio/ video sharing platform / podcasts, etc.)				CAU

Source: Own processing

Results

The crucial role of human capital in the performance of Accelerators is independent of their gender inclusivity (Table 2). To further this understanding, the majority the Accelerators have the same strategy about the recruitment of experienced and/or renowned mentors (EM), apart from the Accelerators that do not have women (co-) founders in their portfolio.

Table 2 Crosstab EM through GINCO (% of women (co)-founders in the portfolio). * Level of significance 1%.

		<i>GINCO</i>					<i>TOTAL</i>	
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>		
EM	0	Count	1	0	1	0	0	2
		% of Total	2%	0%	2%	0%	0%	4.1%
	1	Count	0	21	21	4	1	47
		% of Total	0%	42.9%	42.9%	8.2%	2%	95.9%
TOTAL		Count	1	21	22	4	1	49
		% of Total	2%	42.9%	42.9%	8.2%	2%	100%
<i>Chi-Square Tests</i>								
		<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>		<i>Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)</i>			

Pearson Chi Square	24.618 ^a	4	< 0.001
Likelihood Ratio	8.576	4	0.073
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.575	1	0.209
N of Valid Cases	49		

a. 8 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected is 0.04.

Source: Own processing

Furthermore, Accelerators with low, moderate or high degree of women (co-) founders in their portfolio believe that they should provide easy access to clients or pilot partners (EMA) in contrast with Accelerators without women (co-) founders (Table 3).

Table 3 Crosstab EMA through GINCO (% of women (co)-founders in the portfolio). * Level of significance 1%.

		<i>GINCO</i>						<i>TOTAL</i>
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>		
EMA	2	Count	1	1	0	0	0	2
		% of Total	2%	2%	0%	0%	0%	4.1%
	3	Count	0	2	4	0	0	6
		% of Total	0%	4.1%	8.2%	0%	0%	12.2%
	4	Count	0	10	14	1	0	25
		% of Total	0%	20.4%	28.6%	2%	0%	51%
	5	Count	0	8	4	3	1	16
		% of Total	0%	16.3%	8.2%	6.1%	2%	32.7%
	TOTAL	Count	1	21	22	4	1	49
		% of Total	2%	42.9%	44.9%	8.2%	2%	100%

Chi-Square Tests

	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)</i>
Pearson Chi Square	32.960 ^a	12	< 0.001
Likelihood Ratio	17.253	12	0.140
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.035	1	0.081
N of Valid Cases	49		

a. 8 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected is 0.04.

Source: Own processing

Among them is widely believed that part of their responsibility is to provide substantial financing or support to ensure that startups participating in their programmes have access to necessary funding, without the gender of (co-)founder be an obstacle.

Table 4 Crosstab SFIA through GINCO (% of women (co-)founders in the portfolio). * Level of significance 1%.

		<i>GINCO</i>						
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>TOTAL</i>	
SFIA	1	Count	1	0	0	0	0	1
		% of Total	2%	0%	0%	0%	0%	2%
	2	Count	0	3	2	0	0	5
		% of Total	0%	6.1%	4.1%	0%	0%	10.2%
	3	Count	0	4	1	0	0	5
		% of Total	0%	8.2%	2%	0%	0%	10.2%
	4	Count	0	11	14	2	0	27
		% of Total	0%	22.4%	28.6%	4.1%	0%	55.1%
	5	Count	0	3	5	2	1	11
		% of Total	0%	6.1%	10.2%	4.1%	2%	22.4%
TOTAL		Count	1	21	22	4	1	49
		% of Total	2%	42.9%	44.9%	8.2%	2%	100%

<i>Chi-Square Tests</i>			
	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)</i>
Pearson Chi Square	58.214 ^a	16	< 0.001
Likelihood Ratio	18.848	16	0.277
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.547	1	0.003
N of Valid Cases	49		

a. 23 cells (92.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected is 0.02.

Source: Own processing

In general, European Accelerators acknowledge that the development of mentor pool is not as daunting (CCMP) as it may seem (Table 5). Even though a few of them think that the development of a mentor pool is one of the greatest challenges to overcome – in terms of size, availability and expertise – that seems not to be connected with gender inclusivity, but with other factors.

Table 5 Crosstab CCMP through GINCO (% of women (co-)founders in the portfolio). * Level of significance 1%

		<i>GINCO</i>						
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>TOTAL</i>	
CCMP	1	Count	0	3	7	1	0	11
		% of Total	0%	6.1%	14.3%	2%	0%	22.4%

2	Count	0	11	7	1	1	20
	% of Total	0%	22.4%	14.3%	2%	2%	40.8%
3	Count	0	3	4	1	0	8
	% of Total	0%	6.1%	8.2%	2%	0%	16.3%
4	Count	0	4	4	0	0	8
	% of Total	0%	8.2%	8.2%	0%	0%	16.3%
5	Count	1	0	0	1	0	2
	% of Total	2%	0%	0%	2%	0%	4.1%
TOTAL	Count	1	21	22	4	1	49
	% of Total	2%	42.9%	44.9%	8.2%	2%	100%

Chi-Square Tests

	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)</i>
Pearson Chi Square	34.937 ^a	16	0.004
Likelihood Ratio	18.228	16	0.311
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.558	1	0.455
N of Valid Cases	49		

a. 23 cells (92.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected is 0.04

Source: Own processing

As presented in Table 6, in general Accelerators have different success levels – percentage of startups that got funded (SGF) – based on their gender inclusivity. Specifically, Accelerators with zero or low gender inclusivity experience lower success levels than Accelerators with neutral or high participation of startups with female (co-) founders.

Table 6 Crosstab SGF through GINCO (% of women (co)-founders in the portfolio). * Level of significance 5%.

		<i>GINCO</i>						
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>TOTAL</i>	
SGF	1	Count	1	3	0	0	4	
		% of Total	2%	6.1%	0%	0%	0%	8.1%
	2	Count	0	10	4	2	0	16
		% of Total	0%	20.4%	8.2%	4.1%	0%	32.7%
	3	Count	0	5	10	1	0	16
		% of Total	0%	10.2%	20.4%	2%	0%	32.7%
	4	Count	0	0	5	0	0	5
		% of Total	0%	0%	10.2%	0%	0%	10.2%
	5	Count	0	3	3	1	1	8
		% of Total	0%	6.1%	6.1%	2%	2%	16.3%
TOTAL	Count	1	21	22	4	1	49	
	% of Total	2%	42.9%	44.9%	8.2%	2%	100%	

Chi-Square Tests

	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)</i>
Pearson Chi Square	30.628 ^a	16	0.015
Likelihood Ratio	26.461	16	0.048
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.402	1	0.007
N of Valid Cases	49		

a. 21 cells (84.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected is 0.08.

Source: Own processing

In accordance with the studies conducted by researchers about the role of human capital in firms' success, European Accelerators regardless of their degree of gender inclusivity, believe that they have built a leadership/ management team of highly experienced and qualified members. However, this observation does not hold true for Accelerators without startups with women (co-)founders, also there is a division among Accelerators with high consistency of startups with female leadership (Table 7).

Table 7 Crosstab LELM through GINCO (% of women (co-)founders in the portfolio). * Level of significance 5%.

<i>GINCO</i>		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>TOTAL</i>
LELM	Count	1	0	1	1	0	3
	% of Total	2%	0%	2%	2%	0%	6.1%
	Count	0	1	1	0	0	2
	% of Total	0%	2%	2%	0%	0%	4.1%
	Count	0	6	3	1	0	10
	% of Total	0%	12.2%	6.1%	2%	0%	20.4%
	Count	0	14	17	2	1	34
	% of Total	0%	28.6%	34.7%	4.1%	2%	69.4%
	Count	1	21	22	4	1	49
	% of Total	2%	42.9%	44.9%	8.2%	2%	100%

Chi-Square Tests

	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)</i>
Pearson Chi Square	21.334 ^a	12	0.046
Likelihood Ratio	12.312	12	0.421
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.211	1	0.646
N of Valid Cases	49		

a. 18 cells (90.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected is 0.04.

Source: Own processing

Besides, Accelerators with startups led by women, even though their presence is bounded in Accelerators programmes, they strive for high interaction with relevant public stakeholders, such as government and regional authorities (Table 8).

Table 8 Crosstab HIRPS through GINCO (% of women (co)-founders in the portfolio). * Level of significance 1%.

		<i>GINCO</i>					<i>TOTAL</i>	
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>		
HIRPS	0	Count	1	1	1	0	0	3
		% of Total	2%	2%	2%	0%	0%	6.1%
	1	Count	0	20	21	4	1	46
		% of Total	0%	40.8%	42.9%	8.2%	2%	93.9%
TOTAL		Count	1	21	22	4	1	49
		% of Total	2%	42.9%	44.9%	8.2%	2%	100%

<i>Chi-Square Tests</i>			
	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)</i>
Pearson Chi Square	15.822 ^a	4	0.003
Likelihood Ratio	6.395	4	0.172
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.414	1	0.120
N of Valid Cases	49		

a. 8 cells (80.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected is 0.06.

Source: Own processing

Frequently, there is a reluctance towards women entrepreneurs, stemming from the perception that entrepreneurial ventures are traditionally a male-dominated field. These resulted to limited participation of startups led by women in accelerator's programmes as they could potentially harm their reputation. However, as depicted in Table 9, the Accelerator's level of notoriety does not seem to be related with gender inclusivity. Specifically, Accelerators with moderate or high level of inclusivity have lower levels of notoriety than the others.

Table 9 Crosstab WKN through GINCO (% of women (co)-founders in the portfolio). * Level of significance 1%.

		<i>GINCO</i>					<i>TOTAL</i>	
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>		
WKN	1	Count	1	0	1	0	0	2
		% of Total	2%	0%	2%	0%	0%	4.1%
	2	Count	0	8	9	2	0	19
		% of Total	0%	16.3%	18.4%	4.1%	0%	38.8%
	4	Count	0	8	5	0	0	13
		% of Total	0%	16.3%	10.2%	0%	0%	26.5%
	5	Count	0	5	7	2	1	15
		% of Total	0%	10.2%	14.3%	4.1%	2%	30.6%
TOTAL		Count	1	21	22	4	1	49
		% of Total	2%	42.9%	44.9%	8.2%	2%	100%

<i>Chi-Square Tests</i>			
	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)</i>

Pearson Chi Square	30.016 ^a	12	0.003
Likelihood Ratio	14.910	12	0.246
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.929	1	0.335
N of Valid Cases	49		

a. 14 cells (70.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected is 0.04.

Source: Own processing

As regard the marketing strategy, Accelerators with zero or moderate number of invested startups with a woman as a (co-)founder proceed on unpaid communication activity using mass-media more frequently than Accelerators with high success. In fact, Accelerators with high success with startups led by women tend to proceed on one to two unpaid communication actions (Table 10). In respect to Accelerators with low percentage of invested startups with a woman as a (co-)founder, which does not seem to focus on the unpaid communication activity using mass-media.

Table 10 Crosstab CAP through GINCO (% of women (co-)founders in the portfolio). * Level of significance 5%.

		<i>GINV</i>					
		<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>TOTAL</i>	
CAP	1	Count	0	7	8	1	16
		% of Total	0%	14.3%	16.3%	2%	32.7%
	2	Count	2	7	3	3	15
		% of Total	4.1%	14.3%	6.1%	6.1%	30.6%
	3	Count	0	7	3	1	11
		% of Total	0%	14.3%	6.1%	2%	22.4%
	4	Count	3	1	3	0	7
		% of Total	6.1%	2%	6.1%	0%	14.3%
TOTAL		Count	5	22	17	5	49
		% of Total	10.2%	44.9%	34.7%	10.2%	100%

Chi-Square Tests

	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)</i>
Pearson Chi Square	17.256 ^a	9	0.045
Likelihood Ratio	17.644	9	0.040
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.289	1	0.310
N of Valid Cases	49		

a. 12 cells (75.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected is 0.71.

Source: Own processing

According to Table 11, Accelerators with moderate or high success on funded startups with women (co-)founder slightly eschew the strategy of sponsored communication activity by using their own channels of social media and Google Ads to promote their website (CAS). However, the above strategy is favored by Accelerators without success on invested startups with a woman as a (co-)founder.

Table 11 Crosstab CAS through GINCO (% of women (co-)founders in the portfolio). * Level of significance 1%.

GINV			1	2	3	4	TOTAL
CAS	1	Count	0	4	7	2	13
		% of Total	0%	8.2%	14.3%	4.1%	26.5%
	2	Count	0	9	3	2	14
		% of Total	0%	18.4%	6.1%	4.1%	28.6%
	3	Count	0	6	3	1	10
		% of Total	0%	12.2%	6.1%	2%	20.4%
	4	Count	5	3	4	0	12
		% of Total	10.2%	6.1%	8.25	0%	24.5%
TOTAL		Count	5	22	17	5	49
		% of Total	10.2%	44.9%	34.7%	10.2%	100%

<i>Chi-Square Tests</i>			
	<i>Value</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)</i>
Pearson Chi Square	22.683 ^a	9	0.007
Likelihood Ratio	22.492	9	0.007
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.321	1	0.007
N of Valid Cases	49		

a. 13cells (81.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected is 1.02.

Source: Own processing

Accelerators which run exclusive programs for women showcase differences in respect of the easy of market access and the number of full-time employees (Table 12) at level of significance at 1% and 5% respectively.

Table 12 Mann-Whitney U of EMA and FTE across WEP(programs programmes dedicated to women entrepreneurs (exclusive cohort/program))

<i>Null hypothesis: The distribution of EMA or FTE is the same across categories of WEP</i>		
	<i>EMA</i>	<i>FTE</i>
Reject the Null hypothesis		
Total N	49	
Mann-Whitney U	156.000	148.500
Wilcoxon W	166.000	158.500
Test Statistic	156.000	148.500
Standard Error	24.962	27.155
Standardized Test Statistic	2.644	2.154
Asymptotic Sig.(2-sided test)	.008	.031
Exact Sig.(2-sided test)	.012	.029

Source: Own processing

Accelerators with activities adapted to women entrepreneurs (dedicated mentors, events, financial resources, and network) (AAWE) showcase differences in aspects as the provision of financial grants or investments (FGI), guaranteed financial grants or investments through a related funding arm (GFFA) and wanting fees and/or equity stake (shares) (FES), easy of market access (EMA), level of experience & skills for the teams working with startups

(Leadership/ management team) (LELM) and communication actions used by the Accelerator (CAU) at significance level of 5%. Furthermore, the findings reveal that there are differences with respect to Accelerators’ provisions, when they embrace dedicated support to startups led by women, such as mentors, events, and flexible schedules. In fact, the results were statistically significant at 1% about the distribution of substantial financing or support access to finance substantial financing for the program participants – startups (SFIA), as a substantial access to focused talent pool for any deeptech startup (ATP).

Table 13 Mann-Whitney U of FGI, GFFA, FES, ATP, SFIA, EMA, LELM, CAU and CHR across AAWE (dedicated support to women entrepreneurs such as: mentors, events, financial resources or network, flexible & adapted schedules for women with specific responsibilities)

<i>Null hypothesis: The distribution of FGI/ GFFA/ FES/ ATP/ SFIA/ EMA/ LELM/ CAU or CHR is the same across categories of AAWE</i>									
	<i>FGI</i>	<i>GFFA</i>	<i>FES</i>	<i>ATP</i>	<i>SFIA</i>	<i>EMA</i>	<i>LELM</i>	<i>CAU</i>	<i>CHR</i>
Reject the Null hypothesis									
Total N	49								
Mann-Whitney U	341.50	333.50	340.00	360.50	362.00	337.50	19.50	26.00	36.00
Wilcoxon W	446.50	438.50	445.00	465.50	467.00	442.50	24.50	31.00	41.00
Test Statistic	341.50	333.50	340.00	360.50	362.00	337.50	19.50	26.00	36.00
Standard Error	41.148	38.911	40.558	43.268	40.906	41.186	6.636	9.851	4.103
Standardized Test Statistic	2.345	2.274	2.343	2.669	2.860	2.246	.034	.033	.063
Asymptotic Sig.(2-sided test)	.019	.023	.019	.008	.004	.025	.042	.042	.039

Source: Own processing

Discussion

Analysing the results on gender diversity in European DeepTech accelerator programs, important findings emerge that agree with, but also diverge from, previous studies. First, the study confirms the hypothesis that women's participation in accelerator entrepreneurial programs is limited, which is reflected in the proportion of female founders and invested startups (GEM, 2023). As reported in the literature, this limited proportion is attributed to cultural and social barriers that affect women's access to resources such as funding and mentorship (Brush et al., 2018; Bullough et al., 2019).

One of the most notable findings relates to the role of human capital and mentorship in the success of accelerators. Our study showed that accelerators with stronger human capital and networking through experienced mentors had higher levels of success regardless of female participation. This confirms previous findings linking the value of human capital and experience to the overall performance of entrepreneurial ecosystems (Crook et al., 2011; Campbell et al., 2012). However, accelerators without female leadership were found to be

lagging behind in terms of effectiveness in accessing customers or partners, highlighting the need for tailored inclusion strategies (Crişan et al., 2021).

Our results reinforce this necessity highlighted in previous studies, which note that enhancing the presence of female entrepreneurs through specific mentoring programs can reduce the gender gap (Le Loarne Lemaire et al., 2023). Accelerators that implement programs directed to women, with mentors and appropriate financial tools, have higher investment success rates and easier access to important networks (Dixit and Sinha, 2024).

Overall, our observations highlight a two-pronged strategy. First, there is a need to institutionalize mentoring and financial support programs tailored to the needs of women founders, as the lack of such programs may perpetuate or even reinforce existing inequalities. Secondly, accelerators must recognise the need to integrate women founders into their core activities in a non-discriminatory manner. Especially in the Nordic countries, where the policy emphasis is on overall gender inclusion rather than on targeted programmes, this approach does not seem to achieve as high participation rates of female founders (Callerstig et al., 2024).

For future research, it is suggested to examine the long-term effects of women's participation in accelerators. It could be explored whether their long-term participation contributes to enhancing innovation and the sustainability of startups, while exploring geographical differences between European countries would allow for a more detailed analysis of cultural and political differences. Finally, studying the marketing and communication strategies used by accelerators with different success rates of female startups will help to map effective strategies to attract and support female entrepreneurs at higher levels.

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